

IN EDUCATION OF STUDENTS CREATIVITY ACTIVITY IMPROVEMENT

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Abstract: In the article common medium education in their schools technology innovative pedagogy in the creative activity of students in science classes labor related to making simple items through the use of technology form skills and direct them to consciously choose a profession educational and educational importance illuminated.

Key words: school, student, lesson, class, science of technology, education, education, stage, activity, skill, qualification, profession, interest, hard work, efficiency.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablarida texnologiya fani darslarida o'quvchilarning ijodkorlik faoliyatida innovatsion pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanish orqali oddiy buyumlarni yasashga oid mehnat malakalarini hosil qilish va ongli ravishda kasb tanlashga yo'naltirishning ta'limiy va tarbiyaviy ahamiyati yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: maktab, o'quvchi, dars, sinf, texnologiya fani, ta'lim, tarbiya, bosqich, faoliyat, ko'nikma, malaka, kasb, qiziqish, mehnatsevarlik, samaradorlik.

This is it in the field done being increased some affairs in our republic also at scientific-practical conferences held in many educational institutions discussion reached pedagogical from technologies of use theoretical and practical issues attention being directed. also in our republic in this regard in magazines and

newspapers in the field of education take going affairs wide light up is getting married.

So by doing education technology humanism principles relies on This direction is unique in the sciences of philosophy, pedagogy and psychology of students individual features separately attention to give through appears. Based on these, education related to the science of technology to the following main conceptual approaches in the design of technologies attention to give need

Organization of cooperative education. Democracy, equality, subjects in relation to the equality of the teacher and the student, the purpose and content of the activity together to determine in the eye holds

A problematic approach. Problematic demonstration of the educational process by the student with together cooperation activation methods is one. This in the process of identifying objective conflicts of scientific knowledge and solving them development of dialectical thinking and their practical activities creative respectively apply is provided.

Use of the latest means and methods of providing information, that is, training to the process computer and information technologies attraction to do

The above conceptual approach and direction of technology learning science content, content, educational information from the volume come came out without of teaching the following method and tools choose received:

Teaching methods and techniques: communication, problem method, teacher games, relay, brainstorming, insert, "Let's learn together", pin board, lecture, seminar, argument, convention and others.

Forms of training organization: closed (frontal), group (link, brigade), alone (individual) in order and mutually to cooperation based on

Teaching aids: usual teaching aids (textbook, synopsis, technological card, overhead projector). except graph organizers, computer technique and information technologies.

Mutually contact tools: control the results analysis to do based on teaching perspective planning (diagnosis, diagnosis).

Method and means of management. Technological card of training session planning in view. Stages of technological card training set, placed to the goal in reaching student and of the teacher cooperative activities, of students from class except independent their work identify to get service does.

Monitoring and evaluation. Training session and training throughout the course to monitor the results, student activity every session and year during rating based on evaluation.

In short, educational technology is a part of pedagogy as a part of the laws, regulations for the optimal achievement of the goal of education, method and tools regarding seeker science is considered

Innovative education technologies. Current at the time education new methods - innovative methods are effective in the process of teaching in institutions trying to use it. It is organized on the basis of innovative education to fully understand the essence of the pedagogical processes and to ensure that they are more effective, interesting, and of high quality of methods new-new edges to open possibility is giving

Below innovative – new education methods description to give movement we do

"Innovation" is an English word whose dictionary meaning is "in" - "new", "vation" means "introduction, application, application", i.e. innovation education to the process the news input, apply, app reach means "Brainstorming", "Debate", "Working in groups", "Modified education", "Improvisation", "Multimedia", "Thoughts attack", "Cluster", "Boomerang technology", "Skorobey technology", "Libra technology", "Epigich technology", "Problem situation", "Specific situation, case study", "Critical thinking", "Keep your point of view" and others like that are innovative is one of the educational methods. These methods include ice cream, spider web, chain, brainstorming, cluster, discussion (debate), Glob-alphabet, abstract thinking, zigzag, insert card, stop and read analysis to do like many methods input possible [1-17]. Lessons here so methods based on organized, it will be fun, interesting and meaningful, no student in such a lesson does not get bored; students are more interested in such lessons, in them to participate strong passion harvest will be himself each bilaterally to show chance is created. In lessons such methods apply through in students:

comprehensive, broad and deep thinking, expressing one's opinion freely, lash and protect; events and phenomena, properties of objects understanding and imagination eat get;

of knowledge continuity provide;

to be able to apply theoretical materials in practice, to active practical activities entering go away get;

small in groups and the team inside work to get mutually respect;

independent and creative work like skills harvest to do possible

As a result, students' activities are activated during the lesson, each the student thinks and works, they share each other's views, think- Rini respect they do and own thoughts with they fill. Students between interpersonal social attitude, each other support like traits surface will come

"Blitz game" technology. Technology about briefly information. This technology students actions sequence right organize achieve makes sense to think learning subject based on many different from thoughts from the data need choose to receive to teach directed. This During technology, students express their independent thoughts to others to hold they get because this technology that's it complete conditions by creating gives

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